

MEASURES TO EXPAND STATE POLICY TOWARDS YOUTH AND ACTIVE PARTICIPATION OF THE YOUTH OF NEW UZBEKISTAN IN THE INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND CULTURAL PROCESS

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Abstract. *New Uzbekistan is a country developing on the basis of the principles of friendly cooperation with the world community, strictly adhering to generally accepted norms and principles of democracy, human rights and freedoms, and the ultimate goal of which is the creation of a free, prosperous state.*

Youth policy is part of the state activity of the Republic of Uzbekistan and a priority direction; its goal is the social development of youth and socio-economically, legally and organizationally, in order to mature and fully realize their creative talent in the interests of society. "No matter how difficult it is, we are unique in terms of educating young people and we need to find effective, modern methods.

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Youth is the main driving force giving new meaning and content to large-scale reforms at the national level. Today, young people are appointed to government positions and are entrusted with key positions to manage the social policy of Uzbekistan.

Recently, attention has been focused on the problems of youth and the search for their solutions along with the strategic objectives of the country. Targeted measures taken in accordance with the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On State Youth Policy" dated September 14, 2016, and the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 30, 2020 "On measures to radically reform and raise state youth policy in the Republic of Uzbekistan to a new level" were announced", which defines the tasks arising from this law, as well as declaring June 30 "Youth Day". Uzbekistan has established the state award "Mard Uglon" and the medal "Kelajak bunyodkori" with the aim of encouraging motivated young people who have achieved high results and achievements in various fields. On June 27, 2018, the President signed the Decree "On the State Program "Youth is Our Future". This Decree has become an important document aimed at increasing the efficiency of work in this area; on its basis, the "Youth – Our Future" fund was created. Its main funds are intended for the implementation of advanced ideas and initiatives in various fields.

In the field of state policy on youth affairs in the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is aimed at regulating relations. According to the law "On state policy regarding youth", "State policy on youth affairs in Uzbekistan is implemented by the state for the social development of youth and

their development of intellectual, creative and other potentials of social- economic, organizational and a system of legal measures was defined.”

Creating suitable conditions for realizing the potential of each person. - Shavkat Mirziyoyev .

“Creating the necessary conditions for knowledge, education and upbringing to become the main pillar of the new Uzbekistan will be one of the highest priority areas of our policy,” says Shavkat Mirziyoyev’s program “Together we will build a new Uzbekistan.”

There are a number of international funds, programs and organizations that provide grants and scholarships for study, research, internships abroad, as well as student exchange training.

Higher education is often a core component of a country's economic and social development. As a result, many governments around the world have their own policies for the development and regulation of higher education in their countries. These policies include funding mechanisms, legal frameworks and come in various forms, including quality assurance mechanisms.

Also, special attention in our state is paid to the growth, development and education of women.

Women with high intellectual potential are a society that can achieve high results in all areas of their lives. It is necessary to expand the ranks of female scientists and provide them with sufficient conditions for study and work. These conditions are being created under the leadership of the head of our country and are a clear example of the attention paid to this issue. In particular, PF-87 dated March 7, 2022 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, resolution and resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers № 402 dated June 23, 2020, respectively, in higher educational institutions, technical schools and colleges, including correspondence and educational contracts for women studying in the evening training to provide interest-free loans for education for a period of 7 years, has work experience in the specialty for at least 5 years, but has a higher education; women with families and recommendations of the women's committee mainly for undergraduate courses in state higher educational institutions based on the results of individual tests, with the exception of general parameters admission to study on the basis of a suitable paid contract, as well as higher education on the basis of an additional state grant, institutions take part in a competition for women from low-income families, issue a letter of recommendation and organize their admission to study - this procedure was implemented in practice. In each district, women are active and youth leaders and women mayors of regions, cities and districts, deputies on issues of solving complex problems of women.

As the President said: “Tomorrow, for the prosperity of our planet, it will be about what kind of people our children will grow up to be. Our main task is to create conditions for young people to show their potential.” We can say that today's youth are different - they are socially mature and educated, so it is necessary to solve problems. If education is flourishing in a certain country and more attention is paid to youth, then this country begins to flourish even more, because young people with education have innovative projects, as well as education in the spirit of love for the Motherland - our current reform and main goal. The best investment is education, it is a targeted investment if we invest money in this area, and it will be a huge loss if we do not see it. Also in the world community, for the social protection of youth and the solution of a number of their problems, a number of decisions and resolutions are being developed; these international decisions

- the social, economic and spiritual protection of the youth of the world - is the main task of countries.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan 2020 under the chairmanship of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev On October 8, a video conference was held to increase the role of women and youth in society, and a meeting was held to discuss measures to ensure employment. Social support for the population in the country For this purpose, for the first time in the history of Uzbekistan, financial assistance was provided and a list of families in need of help was compiled, i.e., the “Iron Book”. Now each “Youth Register” has been formed in a microdistrict, district, city and region. “Youth notebook” dated October 8, 2020 socio-economic, legal, psychological who has a need for support, knowledge and vocational training, identification, elimination and control of the problems of unemployed youth. Non-state vocational education centers have been created to develop professional skills among young people and women from the “Reconstruction and Development Fund” and funds in the amount of one million dollars have been allocated for financial support. 10 million of them are young people and professionally trained women, as well as 90 million in advanced training courses. It was used to provide preferential loans to those who completed their studies and received a certificate. 1 million for the cost of training young people and women who completed non-state vocational education courses under the “Social Contract” program, the subsidy amount was spent.

The status of youth work is currently being monitored, the protection of their rights and standard of living is guaranteed in assessing the ongoing work on continuous improvement of the “Global Youth Development Index”, “Youth Progress Index” and “Global Youth Index”, and the “Wellbeing Index” will be separated .

To increase the position of our country in international indices in the implementation of youth policy in the republic to improve with the participation of bodies and institutions in these areas. In recent years, our country has carried out the preparation of a “National Report” reflecting the work done and it will be necessary to announce the results to the world community and international organizations. At the next stage, they participate in the formation of an index of cooperation with foreign organizations and institutions; together, to further improve the situation of the country, we can consider conducting a study. It should be noted that as a result of the work implemented:

- the country’s place in the international rankings and index will improve;
- integration of Uzbekistan into the world community and, in general, a greater policy of openness, strengthening in relation to the world;
- education, health and employment in our country in different sectors and the current situation on gender issues is analyzed, the definition of strategic measures is achieved.

Taking this into account, the international community of Uzbekistan in the field of youth in improving its position in the rankings is implementing the formation of metadata suitable for the purposes. Needless to say, this process is not only statistical in nature. Collection and analysis of data, but also relevant research work in the areas (in collaboration with responsible foreign structures) also requires implementation.

As in all sectors of the modern developing world, the development of unique new views and ideas in youth policy, the use of modern and advanced technologies from foreign countries is of great importance. In state policy regarding youth, our country also pays special attention to the experience and condition of young people abroad and also carefully studies policy mechanisms.

In many countries, state policy in the field of youth has been systematized. The law of this country in this area, activities, goals and includes tasks. In particular, in many European countries: Austria, Albania, Romania, Implementation of state policies regarding youth in countries such as Slovakia. Medium and long-term strategies and programs are used. This One of the beneficial aspects of the programs is that these policies are implemented before promotions, the lives of young people are studied, and various studies are carried out. Identifying problems encountered in the lives of young people and solving them effectively. Elimination methods have been developed.

For example, the state of Albania allows young people to study and find work. Implements a number of targeted policies and programs. In Albania, youth education, employment, we can also look at topics such as health. The Albanian government provides educational opportunities to all the country's youth by developing a variety of activities. The government also provides vocational education programs and also offers auxiliary training pathways such as on-the-job training. It also aims to make it easier for young people to find jobs in the country. One of them is that the government provides financial and other types of support to support young people with their ideas. With the exception of the State of Albania, the State of Moldova has also used the strategy in the development of state policy on youth for 3 years. These strategies are “Youth in 2009-2013”. national strategy on issues”, “Moldova-2020” and “until 2020”. “National Strategy for the Development of the Youth Sector” and this played a very important role in the country’s youth policy. Of course, before these strategies are implemented among young people, various questionnaires and studies were conducted. This country ensures the effective implementation of youth policy. In addition to other countries, there is also a state associated with youth. Has his own style of politics. For example, in Belarus, great importance is paid, mainly to computer literacy among young people.

It is important to study policies about the youth of Uzbekistan and other foreign countries and analyze implementation mechanisms for the following reasons:

- exchange of experience: studying international domestic experience is a valuable lesson for improving youth policy, which can provide experience and direction.
- effectiveness: existing mechanisms and analysis of their results, assessment of which approaches are effective in helping to decide.
- innovation: a new, innovative way to support youth. Uzbekistan is making decisions to increase youth participation at all levels. For this purpose, youth parliaments, allowing active participation, councils and other platforms are created for young people to formulate public policy and influence the life of society. This priority, taking into account the directions concerning the youth of Uzbekistan, is expected that state policy will become a powerful tool for supporting the development and participation of youth in all spheres of life in our country.

Public policies towards youth in different countries have unique characteristics and approaches, such as Sweden, Norway and Denmark. In the Nordic countries the focus is on social protection and aims to ensure youth employment. The main focus in Japan is education and career, public students and youth, expert support, quality education and are actively working to create conditions for further employment. Us youth policy, youth entrepreneurship and youth programs aimed at encouraging volunteerism often develop leadership skills, public life is focused on participation and volunteerism. Singapore's focus on education and what it takes to achieve a successful career is focused on developing skills among young people, with targeted programs to encourage innovative and technological entrepreneurship. Youth policy in Germany, social

protection of youth and employment. France's youth policy aims to increase youth employment, support education and vocational training for young people, and also aims to develop entrepreneurship.

Brand new for 10 years. The implementation of 9 important tasks in the field of youth policy strategy means:

- increasing the working capacity and employment of young people;
- improving the qualifications of young people in their specialty and developing their knowledge in the field of innovation;
- ensure the active participation of young people in society;
- strengthening the health of young people;
- improving the culture of young people in the field of their own safety;
- groups of youth at risk of social isolation, assistance in socialization;
- development of international cooperation among youth, employment of youth migrants;
- inform young people about improved socio-political processes;
- active involvement of youth in the creation of cultural programs.

Thanks to the attention and care of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, today's youth of our country has emerged as a special powerful force and at the same time, young people demonstrate themselves as real creators, a source of inspiration, important participants and creators of the economic, social, cultural, political and spiritual life of Uzbekistan. At the heart of the attention given to youth, this rational policy aimed at realizing their dreams, honor and dignity, a worthy future, providing all the opportunities created for them to be the masters of our future, lies the factor of confidence in youth. We see that the country's leader firmly believes in them.

The President, who considers youth to be the main driving force in bringing new meaning and content to large-scale reforms at the national level, has recommended a large number of young people to important government positions, appointing them to key positions, thereby proving that he is pursuing policies in this regard with a completely new conceptual base. Realizing the need for a targeted social policy in Uzbekistan, where more than 70% of the population are young people, the head of state began to completely update and effectively reform this area.

On the initiative of the President, in order to train personnel with deep knowledge, thinking, and the achievements of modern science, the number of universities in our country has exceeded 140. Almost 30 of them are branches of prestigious higher educational institutions. In 2016, this figure at the republican level was only half of the above number, which was the reason that young people who wanted to get an education went to study at higher educational institutions in other countries of the world. This is no secret to anyone. We must not forget that today's successes are an important step towards increasing the intellectual potential of our youth, their acquisition of modern knowledge and professions. At the same time, over the past five years, the quota for admission to higher educational institutions has been increased 3 times. It should be noted that the President in his speeches especially emphasized that this year 182 thousand young people had the opportunity to become students. Thus, the total coverage reached 28%.

Thus, in Uzbekistan, on the basis of comprehensive measures, the implementation of state youth policy consistently continues, which pursues specific goals, which proves its effectiveness and efficiency. It should be noted that those put forward by the head of state Shavkat Mirziyoyev's 5 important initiatives to establish systematic efforts in the social, spiritual and educational spheres

created a new strategy for the upbringing and education of youth in the history of Uzbekistan. We believe that the attention paid to youth today will produce effective results in the future.

REFERENCES

1. [https://yuz.uz/uz/news/Shavkat - Mirziyoev - Shavkat - Mirziyoev - any - task - related - to - youth - future - is - primary - important](https://yuz.uz/uz/news/Shavkat-Mirziyoev-Shavkat-Mirziyoev-any-task-related-to-youth-future-is-primary-important)
2. "Yangi Ozbekistonni" Birgalikda Kuramiz". Shavkat Mirziyoyevning election program
3. Republican scientific-practical conference on the subject "Yangi O'zbekistonda yoshlarga oid davlat siyosatini amalga oshirish strategiyasi: mavjud vaziyat va rivojlantirish istiqbollari "
4. O'zbekiston Respublikasining 2016 yil 14 sentabrdagi "Yoshlarga oid davlat siyosati to'g'risida" law.
5. Shavkat Mirziyoyev. Yangi O'zbekiston Starategiyasi. – Tashkent: "Uzbekistan" publishing house, 2021.